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**Past, Present, and Future of HNR: Reflections on the Practices and Methods
in Historical Network Research Based on an Online Survey**

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Appendix

Additional graphs, tables and qualitative coding

Keywords

HNR community, HNR methods, network analysis, research practices, historical
network data

Table of Contents

The academic field of HNR

Additional graphs

Fig. A1 Relative numbers of the academic positions of the respondents in a pie chart (n=121)	4
Fig. A2 Years of experience with network analysis methods in absolute numbers (n=120)	5
Fig. A3 Relative numbers of the historical periods the respondent's research project is focused on (n=118)	5

Additional tables

Tab. A1 Absolute and relative numbers of respondents per country (n=120)	6
Tab. A2 Cross-table of the absolute and relative numbers of the respondents' seniority and continent of work (n=120)	6
Tab. A3 Relative and absolute numbers of disciplinary affiliation (n=120, free text field, summarized)	7
Tab. A4 Relative and absolute numbers of mentioned disciplines per respondent (n=120)	7
Tab. A5 Absolute and relative numbers of interdisciplinary collaboration (n=98)	7
Tab. A6 Relative and absolute numbers of frequency of collaboration with colleagues from different disciplines (n=101-110)	8
Tab. A7 Relative and absolute numbers of involvement in the platform "The Historical Network Research Community" (n=67)	8
Tab. A8 General reasons for the use of network analysis (n=66)	9
Tab. A9 Specific interests pursued with network analysis methods (n=86)	9

Qualitative coding

Tab. A10 Qualitatively coded research interest categories (n=60)	10
Tab. A11 Distribution of interest categories per project (n=52)	10

The research practices in HNR

Additional graphs

Fig. A4 Use of programming languages among the respondents (n=69)	11
Fig. A5 Use of network visualization tools among the respondents (n=69)	11

Fig. A6 Use of network data formats among the respondents (n=69)	11
Fig. A7 Use of authority files among the respondents (n=18)	11
Fig. A8 Use of ontology or data model formats among the respondents (n=20)	12
Fig. A9 Time invested or willing to invest in the publication of data and/or methods with open standards (n=20)	12
Fig. A10 Evaluation of the resources provided by “The Historical Network Research Community” (n=54)	12
Fig. A11 Anticipated benefits through the “The Historical Network Research Community” (n=65)	13
Fig. A12 Wishes for specific software development for HNR (n=62)	13
<i>Additional tables</i>	
Tab. A12 Relative and absolute numbers of network construction type per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)	13
Tab. A13 Relative and absolute numbers of node entities per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)	13
Tab. A14 Other nodes entities (free text field, summarized)	14
Tab. A15 Relative and absolute numbers of used edge types per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)	14
Tab. A16 Relative and absolute numbers of edge types per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)	14
Tab. A17 Other types of edges (free text field, summarized)	14
Tab. A18 Relative and absolute numbers of the use of concepts from different fields (n=129)	15
Tab. A19 Relative and absolute numbers of use and knowledge of network analysis methods (n=63)	15
Tab. A20 Relative and absolute numbers of authority file use per respondent (n=69)	15
Tab. A21 Use of authority files (n=18)	15
Tab. A22 Relative and absolute numbers of ontology or data model use per respondent (n=69)	16
Tab. A23 Relative and absolute numbers of experience of publication with open standards per respondent (n=69)	16
Tab. A24 Relative and absolute numbers of experience with publishing code online per respondent (n=69)	16
<i>Qualitative coding</i>	
Tab. A25 Qualitatively coded categories of networks (n=60)	16
Tab. A26 Qualitatively coded problems faced in the research project (n=37, free text answers, grouped and summarized)	17

The academic field of HNR

This part includes additional graphs, tables and information regarding the qualitatively coded categories relevant in the paragraph “The academic field of HNR”.

Additional graphs

Fig. A1 Relative numbers of the academic positions of the respondents in a pie chart (n=121)

Fig. A2 Years of experience with network analysis methods in absolute numbers (n=120)

Fig. A3 Relative numbers of the historical periods the respondent's research project is focused on (n=118)

Additional tables

<i>Germany</i>	0.19 (23)	<i>Belgium</i>	0.04 (5)
<i>United Kingdom</i>	0.14 (17)	<i>Spain, Finland, Turkey, Luxemburg</i>	0.03 (4)
<i>United States</i>	0.13 (15)	<i>Switzerland, Austria, Italy, Denmark</i>	0.03 (3)
<i>France</i>	0.08 (9)	<i>Brazil, Greece, Czech Republic, Argentina, Canada</i>	0.02 (2)
<i>Netherlands</i>	0.06 (7)	<i>Portugal, Israel, Chile, Poland, Taiwan, Norway</i>	0.01 (1)

Tab. A1 Absolute and relative numbers of respondents per country (n=120)

	<i>Asia</i>	<i>Europe</i>	<i>North America</i>	<i>South America</i>	Sum
<i>Professor</i>	0	12	6	1	0.16 (19)
<i>Assistant professor</i>	0	7	2	1	0.08 (10)
<i>Senior researcher</i>	0	6	2	0	0.06 (8)
<i>PostDoc</i>	1	24	2	1	0.23 (28)
<i>Doctoral degree</i>	1	5	1	0	0.06 (7)
<i>PhD student</i>	4	23	1	0	0.23 (28)
<i>Master</i>	0	7	1	0	0.07 (8)
<i>Bachelor</i>	0	1	0	2	0.03 (3)
<i>Other</i>	0	5	2	0	0.06 (7)
<i>Outside academia</i>	0	2	0	0	0.02 (2)
Sum	0.05 (6)	0.77 (92)	0.14 (17)	0.04 (5)	-

Tab. A2 Cross-table of the absolute and relative numbers of the respondents' seniority and continent of work (n=120)

<i>History</i>	0.44 (53)	<i>Philosophy, History of Science</i>	0.04 (5)
<i>Archaeology</i>	0.16 (19)	<i>Computational Sciences, Religious Studies</i>	0.03 (4)
<i>Philology</i>	0.1 (12)	<i>Economics, Engineering Sciences, Information Science, Musicology</i>	0.02 (3)
<i>Physics</i>	0.08 (10)	<i>Mathematics, Architecture, Political Science, Area Studies, Anthropology, Geography</i>	0.02 (2)
<i>Sociology</i>	0.08 (9)	<i>Digital Humanities, Arts, Learning Sciences, Psychology, Neuroscience, Rhetoric</i>	0.01 (1)

Tab. A3 Relative and absolute numbers of disciplinary affiliation (n=120, free text field, summarized)

<i>One Discipline</i>	0.76 (91)	<i>Two Disciplines</i>	0.23 (27)	<i>Three Disciplines</i>	0.02 (2)
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Tab. A4 Relative and absolute numbers of mentioned disciplines per respondent (n=120)

<i>Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>	0.59 (58)	<i>No Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>	0.41 (40)
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Tab. A5 Absolute and relative numbers of interdisciplinary collaboration (n=98)

	1 <i>[never]</i>	2	3 <i>[sometimes]</i>	4	5 <i>[regularly]</i>
<i>History (n=103)</i>	0.04 (4)	0.06 (6)	0.18 (19)	0.16 (16)	0.56 (58)
<i>Digital Humanities (n=110)</i>	0.05 (6)	0.09 (10)	0.3 (33)	0.25 (27)	0.31 (34)
<i>Social Sciences (n=108)</i>	0.18 (19)	0.12 (13)	0.34 (37)	0.14 (15)	0.22 (24)
<i>Computational Sciences (n=107)</i>	0.25 (27)	0.12 (13)	0.26 (28)	0.15 (16)	0.22 (23)
<i>Humanities (n=101)</i>	0.2 (20)	0.19 (19)	0.24 (25)	0.18 (18)	0.19 (19)
<i>Libraries (n=103)</i>	0.42 (43)	0.12 (12)	0.22 (23)	0.16 (17)	0.08 (8)
<i>Information Sciences (n=104)</i>	0.44 (46)	0.15 (15)	0.22 (23)	0.14 (15)	0.05 (5)
<i>Mathematics (n=101)</i>	0.57 (58)	0.15 (15)	0.18 (18)	0.05 (5)	0.05 (5)
<i>Physics (n=103)</i>	0.68 (70)	0.08 (8)	0.1 (11)	0.05 (5)	0.09 (9)
<i>Design (n=102)</i>	0.64 (66)	0.14 (14)	0.13 (13)	0.03 (3)	0.06 (6)

Tab. A6 Relative and absolute numbers of frequency of collaboration with colleagues from different disciplines (n=101-110)

<i>Involved</i>	0.54 (36)	<i>Interested</i>	0.28 (19)	<i>Not Involved</i>	0.18 (12)
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Tab. A7 Relative and absolute numbers of involvement in the platform “The Historical Network Research Community” (n=67)

	1 [not important]	2	3 [important]	4	5 [very important]
<i>Generating new hypotheses</i>	0.0 (0)	0.08 (5)	0.12 (8)	0.27 (18)	0.53 (66)
<i>Testing historical arguments</i>	0.06 (4)	0.05 (3)	0.2 (13)	0.18 (12)	0.51 (34)
<i>Finding missing data</i>	0.21 (14)	0.29 (19)	0.21 (14)	0.15 (10)	0.14 (9)
<i>Data cleaning</i>	0.29 (19)	0.3 (20)	0.21 (14)	0.09 (6)	0.11 (7)

Tab. A8 General reasons for the use of network analysis (n=66)

	1 [not important]	2	3 [important]	4	5 [very important]
<i>Clusters of nodes</i>	0.01 (1)	0.02 (2)	0.2 (17)	0.23 (20)	0.54 (46)
<i>Structural changes in time</i>	0.02 (2)	0.07 (6)	0.2 (17)	0.17 (15)	0.54 (46)
<i>Most relevant nodes</i>	0.02 (2)	0.08 (7)	0.21 (18)	0.17 (15)	0.51 (44)
<i>Influence of edges</i>	0.07 (6)	0.14 (12)	0.28 (24)	0.16 (14)	0.35 (30)
<i>Attribute changes in time</i>	0.08 (7)	0.19 (16)	0.28 (24)	0.21 (18)	0.24 (21)
<i>Data quality</i>	0.07 (6)	0.21 (18)	0.28 (24)	0.16 (14)	0.28 (24)
<i>Structural graph properties</i>	0.08 (7)	0.25 (21)	0.23 (20)	0.13 (11)	0.31 (27)
<i>Detecting missing information</i>	0.15 (13)	0.31 (27)	0.21 (18)	0.18 (15)	0.15 (13)

Tab. A9 Specific interests pursued with network analysis methods (n=86)

Qualitative coding

<i>Network structure</i>	43	<i>Development of network analysis tools/methods</i>	4
<i>Network dynamics</i>	21	<i>Unspecific</i>	8
<i>Temporal network evolution</i>	13	-	-

Tab. A10 Qualitatively coded research interest categories (n=60)

<i>One main research interest</i>	32	<i>Two main research interests</i>	17	<i>Three main research interests</i>	3
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Tab. A11 Distribution of interest categories per project (n=52)

The research practices in HNR

This part includes additional graphs, tables and information regarding the qualitatively coded categories relevant in the paragraph “The research practices in HNR”.

Additional graphs

Fig. A4 Use of programming languages among the respondents (n=69)

Fig. A5 Use of network visualization tools among the respondents (n=69)

Fig. A6 Use of network data formats among the respondents (n=69)

Fig. A7 Use of authority files among the respondents (n=18)

Fig. A8 Use of ontology or data model formats among the respondents (n=20)

Fig. A9 Time invested or willing to invest in the publication of data and/or methods with open standards (n=20)

Fig. A10 Evaluation of the resources provided by “The Historical Network Research Community” (n=54)

Fig. A11 Anticipated benefits through the “The Historical Network Research Community” (n=65)

Fig. A12 Wishes for specific software development for HNR (n=62)

Additional tables

<i>Unipartite</i>	0.57 (52)	<i>Bipartite</i>	0.41 (38)	<i>Multi-partite</i>	0.34 (31)
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Tab. A12 Relative and absolute numbers of network construction type per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)

<i>Persons</i>	0.72 (66)	<i>Objects</i>	0.36 (33)	<i>Complex</i>	0.1 (9)
<i>Places</i>	0.55 (51)	<i>Concepts</i>	0.25 (23)	<i>Other</i>	0.21 (19)

Tab. A13 Relative and absolute numbers of node entities per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)

<i>Text documents (e.g. scientific papers, ancient texts)</i>	8
<i>Collective actors (e.g. firms, organizations, institutions)</i>	7
<i>Events, names</i>	2
<i>Attributes</i>	1

Tab. A14 Other nodes entities (free text field, summarized)

<i>One edge type</i>	0.41 (38)	<i>Multiple edge types</i>	0.6 (55)
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Tab. A15 Relative and absolute numbers of used edge types per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)

<i>Social relations</i>	0.64 (59)	<i>Co-Occurrences</i>	0.45 (41)	<i>Complex</i>	0.12 (11)
<i>Acts of communication</i>	0.52 (48)	<i>References</i>	0.32 (29)	<i>Other</i>	0.11 (10)

Tab. A16 Relative and absolute numbers of edge types per respondent (n=92, multiple answers possible)

<i>Similarity (e.g. shared attribute, vocabulary, Jaccard similarity)</i>	6
<i>Geographic connections</i>	2
<i>Simulated movement, transactions</i>	1

Tab. A17 Other types of edges (free text field, summarized)

<i>SNA</i>	0.88 (114)	<i>Scientometrics</i>	0.15 (19)
<i>Complex systems</i>	0.21 (27)	<i>Other</i>	0.12 (15)

Tab. A18 Relative and absolute numbers of the use of concepts from different fields (n=129)

	<i>Use</i>	<i>Knowledge</i>
<i>Centrality measurements</i>	0.95 (60)	0.05 (3)
<i>Community detection algorithms</i>	0.7 (44)	0.17 (11)
<i>Positional analysis</i>	0.19 (12)	0.38 (24)
<i>Stochastic approaches</i>	0.08 (5)	0.3 (19)
<i>Random graph models</i>	0.05 (3)	0.41 (26)

Tab. A19 Relative and absolute numbers of use and knowledge of network analysis methods (n=63)

<i>Use of authority files</i>	0.26 (18)	<i>No use of authority files</i>	0.74 (51)
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Tab. A20 Relative and absolute numbers of authority file use per respondent (n=69)

	<i>GND</i>	<i>Geonames</i>	<i>VIAF</i>	<i>Wikidata</i>	<i>Other</i>
<i>Persons</i>	0.17 (3)	-	0.33 (6)	0.33 (6)	0.11 (2)
<i>Institutions</i>	0.17 (3)	-	-	0.33 (6)	0.06 (1)
<i>Places</i>	-	0.5 (9)	-	0.17 (3)	0.22 (4)
<i>Objects</i>	-	-	-	0.11 (2)	0.17 (3)

Tab. A21 Use of authority files (n=18)

<i>With data model or ontology</i>	0.29 (20)	<i>Without data model or ontology</i>	0.71 (49)
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Tab. A22 Relative and absolute numbers of ontology or data model use per respondent (n=69)

<i>Experience</i>	0.32 (22)	<i>No experience</i>	0.68 (47)
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Tab. A23 Relative and absolute numbers of experience of publication with open standards per respondent (n=69)

<i>Experience</i>	0.35 (24)	<i>No experience</i>	0.65 (45)
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Tab. A24 Relative and absolute numbers of experience with publishing code online per respondent (n=69)

Qualitative coding

<i>Scientific networks (e.g. publications, authors, institutions)</i>	10	<i>Economic networks (e.g. financial, trade)</i>	4
<i>Archeological materials networks</i>	8	<i>language networks</i>	3
<i>Affiliation networks (e.g. political, professional, religious)</i>	6	<i>urban networks</i>	3
<i>Epistolary networks</i>	5	<i>Other forms of networks (mentioned once)</i>	5
<i>Royal court networks</i>	4	<i>Too unspecific answers</i>	12

Tab. A25 Qualitatively coded categories of networks (n=60)

<i>Network construction</i>	3	operationalization of interactions as links, definition of network boundaries, construction of the network in general
<i>Concepts & theory</i>	7	interpretation of network metric results (3x), linkage of theory and methods, arguing for the benefit of network analysis, underspecified theory, choice of appropriate methods for the research question
<i>Collaboration</i>	9	finding collaboration partners with more IT knowledge (3x), finding collaboration partners for the interpretation of results, finding help with data cleaning, convincing unfamiliar colleagues of the benefits of network analysis, lack of cooperation, lack of willingness to share data, building an interdisciplinary research group
<i>Workflows & methods</i>	12	missing programming skills (2x), complicated R packages, problems querying databases, missing comparative studies, missing analysis instruments for uncertainty and incompleteness, lack of matured common approaches/methods, methods for complex/dynamic data, methods involving advanced mathematical analysis, application of structural network metrics to lexical/ co-occurrence networks, evaluation of use of network metrics for different network types, orientation within the variety of available approaches
<i>Data</i>	36	detection and evaluation of missing data (8x), time-consuming data cleaning (7x), data collection (3x), data organization (3x), data linkage (3x), visualization of missing data (2x), implications of missing data for the interpretation of results (2x), data-comparability over time (2x), messy data (2x), person disambiguation (2x), lack of best-practices and guidelines, data interpretation, data scraping from PDFs, availability of cleaned data

Tab. A26 Qualitatively coded problems faced in the research project (n=37, free text answers, grouped and summarized)